

higher than 3 times that of uninoculated plant extracts were considered to contain the virus.

Both rice accessions and six weed species were infected with RSV (see table). Infected *Oryza* plants showed typical RSV symptoms. Infected *Leersia hexandra* plants also showed symptoms. Weed species not infected with the virus were *Brachiaria distachya*, *B. mutica*, *Chloris barbata*, *Cyperus brevifolius*, *C. difformis*, *Eleusine indica*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*. □

Absorbance at 405 nm in ELISA of extracts of plants infected with RSV after inoculation by RSV-viruliferous BPH. IRR1.

Species	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants (no.)	Absorbance at 405 nm	
			Infected plants	Uninoculated plants (mean)
<i>Oryza australiensis</i>				
Acc. 100882	14	2	0.13-0.48	0.00
Acc. 101397	12	6	0.07-0.29	0.00
<i>O. latifolia</i>	10	3	0.13-4.22	0.01
<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	12	1	0.15	0.04
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	12	1	0.17	0.03
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	16	1	0.25	0.00
<i>Eragrostis tenella</i>	12	3	0.12-0.37	0.04
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	12	3	0.10-0.28	0.00
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	28	5	0.06-0.12	0.00

Differential transmission of tungro (RTV) by green leafhopper (GLH) selected on IR54

A. Muis, M. Sudjak S., A. Bastian, and A. Hasanuddin, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops, P. O. Box 173, Ujung Pandang, South Sulawesi, Indonesia; and R. C. Cabunagan and H. Hibino, IRR1

We compared RTV transmission by a GLH *Nephotettix virescens* colony maintained since 1982 on resistant variety IR54 in the greenhouse and by a colony on TN1, using a selected set of 12 differential varieties. Seven-day-old seedlings in test tubes were inoculated separately at 1 insect/seedling for 24 h, using GLH adults that had fed on RTV-infected Pelita plants. Infection

symptoms (stunting and yellowing) were assessed visually 14 d after inoculation (DAI) and by latex serology 16 DAI.

Higher infection rates were obtained from the IR54 colony on IR28, IR29, IR34, IR50, IR54, IR58, and IR60, with resistances to GLH derived primarily from Gam Pai 30-12-15 (see figure). The latex test showed seedlings mostly were infected with both bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses.

Inoculation with the TN1 colony resulted in infection mainly with RTBV alone.

Regardless of colony, IR26 and IR30 had high RTBV infection. IR36 and IR42 had high infection with both viruses.

These results indicate that GLH selected on IR54 have higher ability to transmit RTBV and RTSV on varieties with Gam Pai 30-12-15 in their parentage. Resistance of IR54 to RTV is conditioned only by its resistance to the GLH vector, not to the RTV-associated viruses. □

Infection (%)

RTV incidence based on symptoms and RTBV + RTSV incidence based on the latex test in rice varieties inoculated at 1 insect/seedling in test tubes by TN1 and IR54 GLH colonies that had fed on Cisadane plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV.

Combined ufra + blast (BI) infection in deepwater rice

Y. Rathaiah, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Titabar 785630, Jorhat District, Assam, India

Ufra disease caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* is spreading rapidly in the deepwater rice

1. Blast lesion (arrow) on the boot of an ufra-affected stem. Assam, India.

areas of Jorhat District, Assam. During a survey of ufra incidence, we also found B1 symptoms on ufra-infected stems.

Ufra symptoms were severe in the deepwater rice variety Kekua. The panicles failed to emerge, remaining completely choked within the boot. The swollen boot looked like a long spindle. (This type of symptom is termed swollen ufra.)

Dark brown elliptical lesions appeared on the boot leaf sheaths of

2. Blast lesion (arrow) on the boot leaf of a half-exserted panicle. Assam, India.

swollen ufra stems. The lesions on the boot spread linearly, reaching up to 1 cm, and were slightly sunk lengthwise to become boat-shaped (Fig. 1). The lesions turned ash gray in the center with fungus sporulation (Fig. 2). We consistently isolated the B1 fungus *Pyricularia oryzae* from the growing edges of the lesions.

Stem nematode was extracted in large numbers from the swollen boots that had B1 lesions. Typical B1 lesions also were present on the flag leaf and the

second youngest leaf of swollen ufra stems. B1 lesions were common on the collars. Nodal B1 also was seen on many stems showing ufra symptoms.

The pathogenicity test with the fungus on detached ufra-infected stems proved B1. The unusual occurrence of B1 on the leaf sheath may be due to alteration of plant physiology caused by the ufra nematode. □

Dot-blot immunoassay (DBI) for detecting rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)

P. Q. Cabauatan and H. Hibino, IRRI; and H. T. Hsu, USDA-ARS, Beltsville, Maryland, USA

We used DBI to detect GSV in extracts of infected rice plants (*Oryza sativa*) and compare conventional rabbit polyclonal antiserum (PAb) and mouse monoclonal antibodies (MAb).

Commercially available (Sigma) enzyme-labeled immunoglobulins (IgG) used as second antibodies were goat antimouse IgG : horseradish peroxidase (GAM IgG : HP), goat antimouse IgG : alkaline phosphatase (GAM IgG : AP), and goat antirabbit IgG : alkaline phosphatase (GAR IgG : AP). Three 1st/2d antibody combinations were tested: MAb/GAM IgG : AP, MAb/GAM IgG : HP, and PAb/GAR IgG : AP.

Leaf samples of GSV-infected plants were ground in Tris buffered saline solution [(TBS), 0.05 M Tris-HCl, 0.15 M NaCl, pH 7.5] and the extracts filtered or centrifuged to remove plant debris. A nitrocellulose membrane [(NM), 15 × 9.2 cm, pore size 0.4 μm] that had been immersed in TBS and air-dried was secured in a Bio-Dot microfiltration apparatus (Bio Rad) to align and standardize dots. A small amount (2.5-20 μl) of extract was put into each well.

The dotted NM was incubated for 60 min in a moist chamber, then immersed for 30 min in blocking solution [0.5 M TBS containing 0.05% Tween 20, 2% polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), and 2% bovine serum albumin (BSA), pH 7.5].